

Detailed Review Paper protocol v. 2

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Detailed Review Paper on Embryonic Stem Cells In Vitro Developmental Toxicity Tests.

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Procedural Notes

The reporting of this systematic scoping review protocol will conform to the PRISMA reporting standards.

Overall project structure and plan

Context

Detailed Review Paper on in vitro developmental toxicity assays with the primary focus on stem cells-derived assays, on request of OECD conducted by the stakeholder working group coordinated by JaCVAM. The working group is using systematic scoping review approach to survey the literature base to put together a list of published in vitro stem cells-based developmental toxicity tests.

Objective

The objective is to conduct a literature search to generate 1) a list of all published in vitro stem cells-derived developmental toxicity tests and 2) a comprehensive list of the features of in vitro stem cells-derived developmental toxicity tests and their key features.

We define “*in vitro* research” as a study in which living parts of animals (including humans) up to and including the level of organisation of tissues, but not whole organs, are exposed to chemicals in order to detect adverse effects. Our definition is intended to exclude: (1) intact animals, (2) whole embryo and *ex vivo* studies (in which whole organs are removed and studied outside the animal’s body) and (3) tissue slices. Our definition includes: studies in cell cultures (including stem cell and organo-typic cultures). Studies into the safety of drugs and other xenobiotic chemicals as well as biological effects of exposure to chemical substance (environmental toxicology) are both included.

Overview of methods

The process :

1. Develop a systematic scoping review of the stem cells-derived embryotoxicity tests in the literature;
2. Compose a comprehensive list of embryonic stem cells tests with essential features in a table format

Systematic scoping review of existing literature

Title

A Systematic Scoping Literature Review of of *In vitro* Embryonic Toxicity Tests. This is a protocol for a systematic scoping review of the existing literature. It is not an update of an existing systematic review.

Registration

Publish protocol in Zenodo.org.

Authors

Primary authors: Nancy C. Baker, Thomas Knudsen, Hajime Kojima, Horst Spielmann, Katya Tsaioun, Noriyuki Suzuki

Support

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Leidos

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria

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- Documents that provide methodologies and primary data using in vitro embryotoxicity tests
 - English language
 - Any date
 - Any publication status

Exclusion criteria

- Whole organism tests (mammals, fish, chicken, nematode)
- Narrative reviews
- Conference abstracts and other publications not containing primary data
- Publications in non-English language

Explanatory Notes for Eligibility Criteria

Information Sources

We will limit the search to PubMed for (embryotoxicity) tests using a search strategy listed herein. We will accept additional information supplied by the Working Group members.

Search Strategy

Search Strategy Notes

The PubMed SR search strategy uses the systematic review filter from Shojania KG, Bero LA. "Taking advantage of the explosion of systematic reviews: an efficient MEDLINE search strategy." *Eff Clin Pract.* 2001 Jul-Aug;4(4):157-62. [[PMID: 11525102](#)]. .

PubMed Search Strategy

(Embryonic stem cells OR iPSc OR Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells OR embryonal stem cells OR "embryonic stem cell"[tw]) AND ((toxicity OR congenital abnormalities OR prenatal exposure delayed effects OR dysmorphogenesis OR dysmorphogenetic OR abnormalities, drug-induced) AND (fetus OR embryo OR embryonic OR embryonic development OR larva OR eggs OR prenatal OR pregnancy OR Gene Expression Regulation, Developmental) AND (chemical OR drug OR compound OR toxicity tests OR High-Throughput Screening Assays)) OR embryotoxicity OR embryotoxicants OR teratogenicity OR teratogens OR developmental toxicity OR developmental toxicants OR teratogenic agents OR "developmental neurotoxicity" OR "developmental cardiotoxicity"

The Abstract Sifter Excel tool was used to build and execute the PubMed search. Queries were developed and tested by evaluating the 51 of gold standard articles supplied by the expert group members. The search was conducted on 2/19/2019 and returned 1,533 PubMed entries.

Data Management

We referred to the [Kohl et al. \(2018\)](#) review of existing tools to identify appropriate screening, data extraction and management software.

- Literature search: Abstract Sifter tool
- Filtering for duplicates: Sciome SWIFT-Review and SWIFT Active Screener
- Screening and selection: SWIFT Active Screener
- Extraction and coding:
 - Bibliographic information, data storage: Excel
 - Coding extracted data: Excel

Selection Process

Screening will be conducted by the working group members and their colleagues.

Screening by title and abstract: Titles and abstracts are to be screened by two reviewers. All titles and abstracts will be screened using the AI-assisted method via SWIFT-AS. In this method, both reviewers will have to agree on inclusion or exclusion. All conflicts will be discussed and resolved in weekly teleconferences and the project manager will resolve the conflict which reviewers are going to be unable to resolve. The AI-assisted software will prioritize abstracts for screening based on relevance. The working group will stop the screening after reaching 95% predicted recall.

Screening by full text: Full texts are to be screened by two reviewers, with discussion to resolve conflict. Reviewers will follow the pre-specified inclusion criteria.

Data collection process

Data extraction forms: Pilot forms drafted in Excel and tested by each reviewer on 10 diverse papers. Forms modified and tested on an additional 5 articles. If determined satisfactory, forms approved and used for extraction.

Data extraction process: Data will be extracted one time with project manager doing quality control of 20% of the entries.

Data items

Data collection will be the minimum amount required for the purpose of aggregating key features of the tests and readily associating them with their source documents. The search strategy, inclusion criteria and full collection of extracted data will be published as a comprehensive data

set for other researchers interested in critical appraisal of in vitro studies to investigate for their own purposes. The data to be collected for this study includes:

- Bibliographic details (title, journal, lead author, year)
- DOI of the paper, if available
- URL of the paper, if available
- PubMed ID of the paper, if available
- Name of test (full name and abbreviation)
- Cell line
- Origin species
- Assay characteristics
- Readout system
- Biological applicability domain
- Chemical applicability domain
- Formal validation (if any)
- Specificity, sensitivity, predictivity
- Year of first publication
- Total Number of publications

Narrative reviews of embryotoxicity tests are included primarily as resources for ensuring full coverage of the literature. Data will only be extracted from publications containing primary data and methods.